

Enhanced IoT Bottleneck Detection: A Hybrid Deep Learning Approach

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing is perhaps the most enticing innovation in the present figuring situation. It gives an expense-effective arrangement by diminishing the enormous forthright expense of purchasing equipment foundations and processing power. Fog computing is an additional help to cloud infrastructure by utilizing a portion of the less-registered undertaking at the edge devices, reducing the end client's reaction time, such as IoT. However, most of the IoT devices are resource-constrained, and there are many devices that cyber attacks could target. Cyber-attacks such as bottleneck, Dos, DDoS, and botnets are still significant threats in the IoT environment. Botnets are currently the most significant threat on the internet. A set of infected systems connected online and directed by an adversary to carry out malicious actions without authorization or authentication is known as a botnet. A botnet can compromise the system and steal the data. It can also perform attacks, like Phishing, spamming, and more. To overcome the critical issue, we exhibit a novel botnet attack detection approach that could be utilized in fog computing situations to dispense with the attack using the programmable nature of the software-defined network (SDN) environment. We carefully tested the most recent dataset for our

proposed technique, standard and extended performance evaluation measures, and current DL models. To further illustrate overall performance, our findings are cross-validated. The proposed method performs better than previous ones in correctly identifying 99.98% of multi-variant sophisticated bot attacks. Additionally, the time of our suggested method is 0.022(ms), indicating good speed efficiency results.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant issues for the network system to be efficient and reliable while doing transactions over the IoT is security. The tremendous growth of IoT in different fields, i.e., surveillance, healthcare, transportation, manufacturing industry, education, and others, encourages securing IoT infrastructure to improve its performance. Earlier IoT devices generate data through various types of sensors, and it becomes tidy for the cloud servers to handle or process these transactions efficiently. Fog computing is among the newly proposed schemes that could be utilized to add preferred features to the IoT infrastructure. Fog computing is competent in doing some regional analysis of information before communicating the aggregated data to the cloud server. It helps in keeping the latency

constraints in some time compelled real-time issues, making them appropriate for IoT-based applications such as vehicular ad-hoc networks (VANETs). These advancements towards using fog servers in IoT infrastructure motivate the adversaries to target the fog server with malicious intent to lower its performance. Hence, security and protection of the system are among the major issues that can affect the performance of fog computing. In this regard, availability is among the core security requirements for offering services to the actual customer applications according to their interest. However, this is constantly tested by the adversaries by launching different types of attacks, such as DoS or DDoS attacks. An individual or a group can perform these attacks. If a group performs it, it is named "botnet," while if an individual launches it, it is known as "bot-master." The bot-master is the attacker node that can launch several types of attacks on the server, such as Phishing, spam, Click fraud, and others. A command-and-control channel remotely controls a botnet. The command-and-control channel is a system the adversary uses to control by sending messages and commands to a compromised system. The adversary can steal the data through these commands and manipulate the infected network. In a botnet attack, some 'n' number of compromised nodes are controlled by a bot-master, and they launch an attack on the server from different compromised systems.

In the fog computing paradigm security is still challenging task, and various security schemes are proposed to make it resilient against vulnerabilities. However, most of the

schemes focus on flexibility and continuous monitoring of the fog server. Software-defined networking (SDN) is used at fog servers to address flexibility, and continuous monitoring issues. SDN is an emerging networking paradigm that assists in making the network more flexible that can help in managing the network, analyzing the traffic, and assisting in the routing control architectures as there is a separate control plan that provides a flexible device management policy. Hence, an SDN-based fog computing environment provides centralized control to the fog computing system. The characteristics of the SDN based fog computing system are discussed below

- _ SDN can manage the secure connection for thousands of devices connected over the fog for data transmission.
- _ SDN can provide real-time monitoring and awareness with low latency.
- _ SDN can dynamically balance the load with its flexible architecture.
- _ SDN can customize the policies and applications due to its programmable nature.

The software-defined network plays a vital role as its network control architecture can be directly programmable through the command requests. SDN based fog computing architecture can assist in analyzing and managing IoT devices. The motivation behind SDN is to give consistency to network management through partitioning the network into the data plane and the control plane. SDN can add programmability, adaptability, and versatility to the fog computing system. In high-speed networks, discovering the botnet attack is a significant concern. The proposed work shows the

methodology through which the botnet attack is identified with a high detection rate which can be used in SDN to enhance the security of fog computing. Deep learning (DL) based detection approach in the SDN-based fog computing application can be a better counterattack to improve the overall performance of the system [20]. DL strategy is adaptable to conditions to recognize the abnormal behavior of the network. We proposed a hybrid deep learning detection policy to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the SDN-based fog computing architecture. Results show that the proposed scheme works better and provides a better detection rate.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

“Secure IIoT-enabled industry 4.0,”

The Industrial Internet of things (IIoT) is the main driving force behind smart manufacturing, industrial automation, and industry 4.0. Conversely, industrial IoT as the evolving technological paradigm is also becoming a compelling target for cyber adversaries. Particularly, advanced persistent threats (APT) and especially botnets are the foremost promising and potential attacks that may throw the complete industrial IoT network into chaos. IIoT-enabled botnets are highly scalable, technologically diverse, and highly resilient to classical and conventional detection mechanisms. Subsequently, we propose a deep learning (DL)-enabled novel hybrid architecture that can efficiently and timely tackle distributed, multivariant, lethal botnet attacks in industrial IoT. The proposed approach is thoroughly evaluated on a current state-of-the-art, publicly available dataset using standard performance evaluation

metrics. Moreover, our proposed technique has been precisely verified with our constructed hybrid DL-enabled architectures and current benchmark DL algorithms. Our devised mechanism shows promising results in terms of high detection accuracy with a trivial trade-off in speed efficiency, assuring the proposed scheme as an optimal and legitimate cyber defense in prevalent IIoTs. Besides, we have cross-validated our results to show utterly unbiased performance.

“GeoFog4Health: A fog-based SDI framework for geospatial health big data analysis,”

Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) is an important framework for sharing geospatial big data using the web. Integration of SDI with cloud computing led to emergence of Cloud-SDI as a tool for transmission, processing and analysis of geospatial data. Fog computing is a paradigm where embedded computers are employed to increase the throughput and reduce latency at the edge of the network. In this study, we developed and evaluated a Fog-based SDI framework named GeoFog4Health for mining analytics from geo-health big data. We built prototypes using Intel Edison and Raspberry Pi for studying the comparative performance. We conducted a case study on Malaria vector-borne disease positive maps of Maharashtra state in India. The proposed framework had provision of lossless data compression for reduced data transfer. Also, overlay analysis of geospatial data was implemented. In addition, we discussed energy savings, cost analysis and scalability of the proposed framework with respect to efficient data processing. We compared the

performance of the proposed framework with the state-of-the-art Cloud-SDI in terms of analysis time. Results and discussions showed the efficacy of the proposed system for enhanced analysis of geo-health big data generated from a variety of sensing frameworks.

“Fog computing security: A review of current applications and security solutions,”

Fog computing is a new paradigm that extends the Cloud platform model by providing computing resources on the edges of a network. It can be described as a cloud-like platform having similar data, computation, storage and application services, but is fundamentally different in that it is decentralized. In addition, Fog systems are capable of processing large amounts of data locally, operate on-premise, are fully portable, and can be installed on heterogeneous hardware. These features make the Fog platform highly suitable for time and location-sensitive applications. For example, Internet of Things (IoT) devices are required to quickly process a large amount of data. This wide range of functionality driven applications intensifies many security issues regarding data, virtualization, segregation, network, malware and monitoring. This paper surveys existing literature on Fog computing applications to identify common security gaps. Similar technologies like Edge computing, Cloudlets and Micro-data centres have also been included to provide a holistic review process. The majority of Fog applications are motivated by the desire for functionality and end-user requirements, while the security aspects are often ignored

or considered as an afterthought. This paper also determines the impact of those security issues and possible solutions, providing future security-relevant directions to those responsible for designing, developing, and maintaining Fog systems.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

The research contribution includes the comprehensive evaluation of botnet attacks for different IoT devices and evolving cyber threats in IoT using the dataset N_BaIoT 2018. Our proposed hybrid technique comprises two DL algorithms: DNN and LSTM. We rigorously evaluate the proposed mechanism with standard performance metrics (i.e., Recall, Accuracy, F1-Score, Precision, AU-ROC, etc.). The presented hybrid scheme results show better detection accuracy with low computational complexity. The contributions of this research work are as given below:

- We suggest an efficient deep learning framework for detecting Botnet attacks in an SDN-based fog computing environment.
- The practical experiment is performed on N_BaIoT Dataset, which comprises both Botnet attack and benign samples.

Disadvantages System

- An existing system is not hybrid deep learning detection policy to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the SDN-based fog computing architecture. Results show that the proposed scheme works better and provides a better detection rate.
- can't customize the policies and applications due to its programmable nature.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We suggest a hybrid DL approach integrating DNN and LSTM to identify IoT botnet attacks. Hybrid models are pretty effective at getting high detection accuracy in a short amount of time [. Therefore, to benefit from many DL classifiers simultaneously, we have taken into account DNN and LSTM to enhance the final results. IoT devices produce massive amounts of surge data quickly; therefore, in the suggested approach, LSTM is considered owing to its capacity to perform effective learning for longer data sequences. In contrast, DNN is used to increase the algorithm’s predictive capability by enhancing speed efficiency. The proposed architecture is depicted in Figure 2, and Table 5 elaborates on the specific configuration of the hybrid architecture we have presented.

Advantages System

- System can manage the secure connection for thousands of devices connected over the fog for data transmission.
- System can provide real-time monitoring and awareness with low latency.
- System can dynamically balance the load with its flexible architecture.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Architecture Diagram

6. IMPLEMENTATION

MODULES:

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Login, Train & Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Prediction Of Attack Type, View Attack Type Ratio, Download Predicted Data Sets, View Attack Type Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user’s details such as, user name, email, address and admin authoriges the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like REGISTER AND LOGIN, PREDICT ATTACK TYPE, VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

7.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

SDN-based fog computing architectures are the trending networking paradigms for several applications based on the IoT infrastructure. Fog computing systems are vulnerable to various types of Botnet attacks. Hence, there is a need to integrate a security framework that empowers the SDN to monitor the network anomalies against the Botnet attacks. DL algorithms are considered more effective for the IoT-based infrastructures that work on unstructured and large amounts of data. DL based intrusion detection schemes can detect Botnet attacks in the SDN-enabled fog computing IoT system.

We created a framework that utilizes a hybrid DL detection scheme to identify the IoT botnet attacks. It is trained against the dataset that contains normal and malicious data, and then we used this framework to identify botnet attacks that targeted different IoT devices. Our methodology comprises a botnet dataset, a botnet training paradigm, and a botnet detection paradigm.

Our botnet dataset was built using the N_BaIoT dataset, which was produced by

driving botnet attacks from the Gafgyt and Mirai botnets into six distinct types of IoT devices. Five attack types, including UDP, TCP, and ACK, are included in both Gafgyt and Mirai attacks. We developed a botnet detection based on three hybrid models_ DNN-LSTM, CNN2D-LSTM, and CNN2D-CNN3D. Using this training model as a foundation, we developed a botnet detection paradigm that can recognise significant botnet attacks. The botnet detection approach is part of a multiclass classification model that can distinguish between the sub-attacks and innocuous data. The fact-finding analysis showed that our hybrid framework DNN-LSTM model had the highest accuracy of 99.98% at identifying the gafgyt and Mirai botnets in the N_BaIoT environment. In 2014 and 2016, the gafgyt and Mirai botnets essentially targeted home routers and IP cameras. The NBaIoT dataset we used for our experiments revealed that rather than the type of IoT devices, the type of training models has a more significant impact on botnet detection performance. We think creating DNN-LSTM-based IoT botnet detection models would be an excellent strategy to enhance botnet identification for different IoT devices.

In the future, we have in mind to compare the performance of the proposed hybrid algorithm to that of other IoT datasets with a more considerable number of nodes. Further, there is a need to test more combinations of DL algorithms and traditional machine learning algorithms.

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